

Collatz Conjecture; No other positive integer loops?

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Abstract

This paper demonstrates that there are no other positive integer loop solutions than the 4, 2, 1 loop. All positive integer loop solutions are encompassed by the equation $(3x+1)/y = x$, for which there is only one solution that adheres to the rules put forth by the Collatz Conjecture, namely $y = 4$ and $x = 1$.

Introduction

The Collatz Conjecture postulates that all positive integers will fall into the infamous 4, 2, 1 loop. In theory there are three possible scenarios:

1. There are no more loops and there is a number(s) that can avoid the 4, 2, 1 loop numbers and increase forever. Which means that the conjecture is false.
2. There are no more loops but there are no numbers that can avoid the 4,2,1 numbers so the conjecture is true.
3. There are more loops and the conjecture is false.

I believe that scenario 3 is incorrect for all positive integers and that is what I will demonstrate in this analysis.

Main Result

The complexity of possible positive integer loops of the Collatz Conjecture are constrained by the fact that all possible loops within the positive integer version of this conjecture have a very specific structure.

Let's demonstrate this by using the 4, 2, 1 loop as an example. The 1 in this model is the "starting number" of the loop. The 4 is the "end number" of the loop. When analyzing the nature of the Collatz Conjecture it is evident that every "starting number" will always be odd and any "end number" will always be even. The 4, 2, 1 loop consists of only three numbers but for the positive integer version of this conjecture, the only other numbers in a loop between the "starting number" and "end number" will be even and divisible by 2 all the way down to the "starting number" which is odd. This means that the "end number" will always be divisible by a positive integer. So let's sum up and put it in mathematical terms.

1. The "starting number" multiplied with 3, and added with 1 will equal the "end number".
2. The "end number" will always be divisible by a positive integer to get you back to the "start number" Let's call this positive integer y .
3. This means that we can formulate a generalized expression for all possible loops in the following way $(3x+1)/y = x$.

Proof

The only solution where x and y are positive integers are when $x = 1$ and $y = 4$.

$(3x + 1)/y = x$ rearranges to

$3x + 1 = xy$ solving for x we get

$$x = 1/(y - 3)$$

For x to be a positive integer, $1/(y - 3)$ must also be a positive integer, this implies that $y - 3$ must be a divisor of 1. The divisors of 1 are ± 1 . Given that x and y are supposed to be positive integers we consider only $y - 3 = 1$:

$$y = 4 \quad \text{and} \quad x = 1/1 = 1$$

So the only positive integer solution for (x, y) is $(x, y) = (1, 4)$.

Conclusion

By excluding scenario 3 we can get closer to a solution of the Collatz Conjecture where the focus will lie on proving if indeed a number can avoid all the numbers that will iterate the sequence back to the 4, 2, 1 loop, and thereby continue to increase its value into infinity.

References

1. Original Collatz Conjecture Paper:

- Collatz, L. "On the origin of the $3n+1$ problem." *Mathematische Annalen*, vol. 21, 1937.

2. General Overview and Surveys:

- Lagarias, J. C. "The $3x+1$ problem: An annotated bibliography (1963–1999)." arXiv preprint math/0309224, 2003.
- Lagarias, J. C. "The $3x+1$ problem and its generalizations." *The American Mathematical Monthly*, vol. 92, no. 1, 1985, pp. 3-23.

3. Further Reading on Iterative Processes:

- Crandall, R. "On the $3x+1$ problem." *Mathematics of Computation*, vol. 32, no. 144, 1978, pp. 1281-1292.
- Chamberland, M. "An update on the $3x+1$ problem." arXiv preprint math/0211084, 2002.